

DEVELOPMENT OF FIBER TOW SPREADING SYSTEM AND ITS APPLICATION FOR THIN FIBER REINFORCED MATERIALS

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1 Introduction

Recently fiber reinforced materials have been widely applied as structural and/or functional materials in the various fields. Especially in sporting goods, fiber reinforced plastics and other type of fiber reinforced materials have been used as main component such as tennis racket, golf club, yacht, etc. In yacht application, several types of fiber reinforced materials have been used. For example, deck, hull and mast are made of carbon or glass fiber reinforced plastics, and sail is consisted of PET or nylon sheet reinforced by fibers. Other type of sail is PET or nylon sheet reinforced by fiber aligned adhesive tapes as shown in Fig.1[1]. In this application wide and thin tape is demanded to achieve the optimal sail properties. In order to satisfy this demand thin reinforcing fiber, i.e. spread fiber tow, is required. There exist various kinds of tow spreading methods such as using pneumatic, ultrasonic, etc. [2-11]. However, these methods require very complex and expensive system and it is difficult to expand their applications such as attaching to conventional molding/manufacturing machines.

Recently spread fiber tow has been also focused in fiber reinforced plastics. By using the thin fiber tow as reinforcement the weakness of the interlayer might be solved and it brings easiness of resin impregnation even in high-viscous thermoplastic composites. Therefore it is important to establish the new and simple fiber spreading system to achieve the advanced composite with better mechanical properties.

From these backgrounds, this study tried to develop the new fiber spreading system. Fibers were spread by mechanical method, and as first trail, the spread fiber reinforced adhesive tape was developed. The effect of fiber spreading on the mechanical properties was evaluated by tensile

properties. In addition, the tensile property was evaluated for the spread fiber laminated between plastic films.

2 Development of Fiber Tow Spreading System

2.1 Mechanism of Fiber Spreading: 1st Approach

In the early stage of this work the suitable process was investigated to establish the effective fiber spreading system. At first, the plate with arc edge was applied to spread the fiber tow. Fig.2 illustrates the first version of our developed fiber spreading system. Fiber tow was drew out from the bobbin by driving roller A, and it was supplied to the spreading plate. This spreading plate had the arc-shaped edge and it was pushed down against the fiber tow. Both by the tension of fiber tow, arc-

Fig.1 Example of yacht sails reinforced by fiber aligned adhesive tapes [1].

Fig.2 1st version of the developed fiber spreading system.

Fig.3 Fiber spreading part of the 1st developed system.

Fig.4 Example of fiber tow spread by the 1st developed system.

Fig.5 Unstable fiber states during fiber spreading process.

shape of the plate edge and the push-down force by the plate the, fiber tow was spread into thin filament layer. Fig.3 is the fiber spreading part of the developed system and Fig. 4 is the example of fiber spread by this system. Here, ultra high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) fiber (Dyneema SK60, 1760dtex, 1560filaments, Toyobo Co., Ltd., Japan) was used for the trial. The width of the

original fiber tow was approximately 2mm and it was spread to maximum 10mm. In this system, however, the width after spreading was not stable and the fiber strayed away from the center of the arc in the plate as shown in Fig.5. The problems of this system are summarized as follows;

Fig.6 2nd version of the developed fiber spreading system.

Fig.7 Fiber spreading roller for 2nd developed system.

- Problem I The track of the fiber during spreading process was unstable.
- Problem II The width of the spread fiber was unstable.
- Problem III It was difficult to control of fiber spreading when the original fiber tow had some distortion.

2.2 Improvement of Fiber Spreading Process and Development of Manufacturing System for Spread Fiber Tow Reinforced Adhesive Tape

As summarized in the previous section the 1st version of developed fiber spreading system had some problems which should be solved. In order to solve these problems several improvements were attempted in the 2nd version of fiber spreading

system. Fig.6 illustrates the newly developed fiber spreading system with taping process. This system was consisted of several sections; fiber driven section, fiber spreading section, taping section and winding section. In order to solve Problem I, the guide bars were attached at several places to stable the track of the fiber movement in fiber driven section. The spreading plate with arc-shaped edge in 1st developed system was effective to spread the fiber tow, however, it derived the unstable movement of the fiber as a result of the friction force between fiber and plate edge. To solve this problem the spreading plate was replaced by the roller with the inserted plates with arc-edge as shown in Fig.7. The problem of the unstable width of the spread fiber was attempted to solve by spreading fiber in the liquid environment. In this process it is assumed that the surface tension might prevent the undesirable separation of the fiber tow. In order to produce spread fiber reinforced tape the adhesive taping process was also introduced after fiber spreading process in this system. Fig.8 illustrates the details of the fiber spreading process. Here, toluene was used as liquid which was selected as ineffective solvent against the adhesive used in the taping process. In order to spread fiber effectively the spread roller was rotated opposite the fiber drawing direction (the roller rotated counterclockwise in Fig.8). After spreading fiber it advances the taping process. The spread fiber is laminated between adhesive sheet and release film

Fig.8 Roller system for fiber spreading.

Fig.9 Developed fiber spreading and taping system and example of spread fiber.

Fig.10 UHMWPE (a) and aramid (b) fibers spread by the developed system.

by rolling process. The adhesive sheet used here was acrylic-based adhesive (#784 (thickness: 60 μ m, Ebisu Chemical Co., Ltd.), and the release film was PET film with 25 μ m thickness. Fig.9 is the outside view of the developed fiber spreading and taping system and the spread fiber in taping process. By

using this system UHMWPE fiber and aramid fiber were tried to spread. Fig.10 shows UHMWPE and aramid fiber after spreading. The original widths of these fibers were approximately 2mm. UHMWPE fiber was spread to 13mm and aramid fiber was to 15mm. If the fiber was successfully spread into

Fig.11 Spread UHMWPE fiber reinforced adhesive tape.

mono-filament layer level, the width of the fiber should be approximately 19mm. The results were a little narrow compared with it, however, it is considered that the obtained width was enough to use the reinforcement of the adhesive tape for yacht sail. Fig.11 shows the spread UHMWPE fiber reinforced adhesive tape obtained by the developed system. In production of this adhesive tape, 200-300m length tape was obtained without any rearrangement of fiber and stable spread fiber was obtained.

In the developed system the roller with arc-edge plates was supposed to contribute to spread fiber by contacting the fiber on the arc-edge plates. In fact, however, the roller induced the water current around it, and it also might contribute to spread fiber effectively.

In our 1st step UHMWPE fiber was chosen for checking the developed fiber spreading system and for producing the reinforced adhesive tape. UHMWPE fiber has high strength and modulus, however, it is not suitable for reinforcing the plastics matrix because it does not have reactive function with sizing and/or plastics matrix. In addition, adopted UHMWPE fiber was non-sized fiber and it is not usual in case of the reinforcing fiber for polymer matrix composite. In our 2nd step, therefore, carbon fiber was attempted to spread using our developed system. 12K carbon fiber with sizing was tried to spread by the developed spreading system. This attempt has just started, however, carbon fiber was much easier to spread by the developed system compared with UHMWPE fiber. In the developed system maximum width of spread fiber at final section was set at 25mm. 12K carbon fiber could spread to about 50mm at intermediate section. Unfortunately carbon fiber could spread wider, however, uniformity was not acceptable and spread fiber tow was separated into

Fig.12 Geometry of tensile test specimen.

Fig.13 Tensile load-elongation curves for sail sheets supported by fiber reinforced adhesive tapes.

several portions. In our future work we will try to control the uniformity of the obtained spread fiber.

3 Tensile Properties of Spread fiber Reinforced Sail Sheet and Spread Fiber Reinforced Polymer Film

3.1 Tensile Properties of Yacht Sails with Spread Fiber Tow Reinforced Adhesive Tape

In order to verify the effect of fiber spreading on reinforcing performance the tensile test was performed for yacht sail material. The sail material used was PET based sail sheet, and the UHMWPE fiber reinforced adhesive tape manufactured by the developed system was adhered on the specimen surface. The geometry of the tensile test specimen is shown in Fig.12. In practical application fiber reinforced adhesive tape is adhered on one side of the sail, and therefore, the adhesive tape with spread fiber was adhered on one side of the specimen. As reference the adhesive tape reinforced by the original fiber (non-spread fiber) was also adopted as reinforcement of the sail. In addition, the original sail sheet without any reinforcement was also tested. Tensile test was performed at a constant cross-head speed of 5mm/min with 100mm gauge length by

Instron type universal testing machine (Autograph AG-50KNI, Shimadzu Corp.). Here, two types of reinforcing conditions were adopted to check the gripping effect of the fiber. One was the specimen with the one fiber placed through top to end of the specimen, and the other was the specimen in which the fiber was placed only between the end-tubs. The fiber was fully gripped in the former specimen and it was not gripped in the latter specimen.

Fig. 13 shows the tensile load-elongation curves for the tested specimens. In this figure annotation (cut) indicates the specimen in which one fiber was placed only between the end-tubs and fiber did not chuck by grip during tensile test. Annotation (end) indicates the specimen with one fiber placed through top to end of the specimen and fiber was chucked by grip during tensile test. By adhering the fiber reinforced adhesive tape onto the sail sheet the initial slope in the load-elongation curves were enhanced, and its effect was much higher in the spread fiber reinforced one. In the (end) specimens the rigidity and the failure load was enhanced significantly because the fiber was gripped at the end of the specimen. Even in the (cut) specimens the rigidity was quite high compared with the non-reinforced sail sheet. By comparing the spread and non-spread fiber the spread fiber specimen showed better tensile properties. In the (cut) specimens, however, the adhesive tape did not follow the elongation of the sail sheet, and as a result, the reinforcing effect was a little at higher load level. Even in this case, the failure load in the spread fiber (cut) specimen showed higher value compared with the non-reinforced sail sheet and the non-spread (cut) specimens. Therefore it is clear that the spread fiber is much effective to enhance the rigidity and strength of the sail.

3.2 Tensile Properties of Spread Fiber Tow Reinforced Polymer Film

The goal of this work is to establish the manufacturing process of the spread fiber reinforced polymer composite materials. At this moment, however, the fiber spreading system was not combined with the composite manufacturing process. In the previous section the spread fiber tow reinforced adhesive tape was manufactured and the effect of spread fiber on tensile properties was evaluated. This material was not actually composite material. In this section, therefore, spread fiber tow reinforced polymer film composite was prepared and the tensile test was performed in order to evaluate the spread fiber on the mechanical properties.

Fig.14 Tensile load-elongation curves for fiber reinforced PET films.

Material used was UHMWPE fiber as reinforcement and polyester (PET) film as laminated material. The PET films were commercially available for paper lamination and its thickness was 100 μ m. Here, the spread fiber was laminated between 2 PET films by heating at 120 $^{\circ}$ C. The prepared fiber laminated film was cut into tensile test specimen. The geometry of the specimen was the same shown in Fig.12. In this case the fiber was placed through top to end of the specimen and fiber was chucked by grip during tensile test. In order to evaluate the effect of fiber spreading the specimen reinforced by non-spreading fiber was also prepared. Tensile test was performed at a constant cross-head speed of 5mm/min with 100mm gauge length by Instron type universal testing machine (Autograph AG-50KNI, Shimadzu Corp.).

Fig.14 shows the tensile load-elongation curves for the spread and non-spread fiber reinforced PET films. As reference the result of the non-reinforced PET film was also indicated. The PET only specimen showed ductile behavior and the significant elongation appeared over 200N. This specimen eventually failed at the elongation of about 40mm. The specimen reinforced with non-spread fiber showed reinforcing effect and the rigidity at low elongation and maximum load were enhanced. After maximum load, however, the load decreased gradually with increasing the elongation. It is considered that not so many filaments broke at the maximum load and remaining filaments still support some load after the peak load. This behavior suggested that some of the filaments supported the applied load during loading process and other filaments did not adhere with PET film. As a result,

ductile behavior appeared after the maximum load. The specimen reinforced with spread fiber showed much higher reinforcing effect compared with that reinforced with non-spread fiber and the rigidity and maximum load were significantly improved than the specimen reinforced with non-spread fiber. In addition, the load suddenly dropped after the maximum load. This behavior was quite different with the non-spread fiber reinforced specimen. The spread fiber aligned as thin filaments layer compared with non-spread fiber and most of the filaments in the tow could contact directly with PET films. This geometrical change contributed to obtain better adhesion between fiber tow and PET films. As a result, most of the filaments could support the applied load and they broke simultaneously at maximum load. Then the load dropped suddenly soon after the peak load. Therefore spread fiber can establish better fiber/matrix interfacial property than the non-spread fiber. This is the most important advantage in usage of spread fiber as reinforcement. In case of thermoplastic matrix composite high viscosity of melt resin induces the difficulty of resin impregnation into fiber tow. By using the spread fiber the resin impregnation process might be omitted and thin thermoplastic composite intermediate material might be available just by coating the thermoplastic resin onto the spread fiber.

4 Conclusion

This study developed new fiber spreading system to obtain thin and widely reinforced material. The fiber was spread by using the roller with arc-shaped plate. The fiber contacted to the counter rotated roller in liquid environment and it was spread successfully. The fiber spreading was achieved by repetition of contact-noncontact with arc-shaped plate and the water current produced by rotation of roller in liquid. The spread fiber was laminated between adhesive sheet and release film, and eventually the spread fiber reinforced adhesive tape was successfully obtained. The tensile test was performed for the sail material reinforced by the spread fiber reinforced adhesive tape. The rigidity and the strength of the sail were well improved by using the spread fiber reinforced adhesive tape. In addition, the spread fiber was laminated with PET films as similar material with composite laminate. Also in this case, the spread fiber achieved higher tensile properties compared with the non-spread fiber reinforced specimen. In the spread fiber most of filaments in fiber tow could be contacted with PET film and this brought the higher interfacial

property. This result suggested that the better interfacial property could easily established in the fiber reinforced composites, even in the fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites. In our future work this developed system will be modified for carbon fiber application and will be tried to combine this system to conventional composite manufacturing system such as extruder, prepregging machine, etc.

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